

STATUS OF EDUCATION SERVICE CONTRACTING (ESC) PROGRAM IN REGION VIII: A MULTIPLE CASE STUDY

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Status of Education Service Contracting (ESC) Program in Region VIII: A Multiple Case Study

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Abstract

This study investigated the problems encountered in implementing the ESC program, how those issues were addressed, and the suggested recommendations raised by the participants. The study employed a qualitative-multiple case study method which involved 12 administrators and 24 teachers in twelve ESC-participating schools in Region VIII. Results indicated that ESC schools have plenty of slots, but most of these slots were unused, especially during the SY 2020-2021 with the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic. Findings revealed that among ESC participating schools in the region, their curriculum is well-implemented, facilities are accessible and adequate, the administration has a good rapport with all their stakeholders, student services are well-delivered despite the hard lockdown, and teachers are personally satisfied because of the professional and spiritual growth. However, the school is struggling financially, and teachers have low salaries. Nevertheless, they find ways to address these problems, highlighting the potential for improvement and the dedication of the educators. Some of the recommendations are the increase of the subsidies, early release of these subsidies, higher salaries for teachers, systematic processing of documents, and monitoring of the academic achievement of the grantees, which all point to a promising future for the ESC program.

Keywords: *education service contracting, ESC implementation, curriculum, subsidy*

Introduction

The 1987 Constitution and RA 6728, Sec. 2, stipulates that the state has a policy on promoting and making quality education available to all Filipino citizens through the Education Service Contracting (ESC) subsidy. This is in response to this need for quality education for public school students while mitigating the influence of the universalization of secondary education in the private education sector (Saguin, 2019). It is a subsidy allocated under the Government Assistance to Students and Teachers in Private Education (GASTPE) based on Republic Act No. 6728 to make quality education on the secondary level more accessible to poor elementary school graduates who deserve financial assistance. It was further amended by Republic Act 8545, the Expanded Government Assistance to Students and Teachers Private Education (E-GASTPE), and acquiesced with Article XIV, Section 3 of the 1987 Constitution of the Republic of the Philippines. The section states that “the government must establish and maintain a system of scholarship grants, student loan programs, subsidies, and other incentives available for deserving students.” The grant must be given not just in public schools but also in private schools, especially to the underprivileged.

The program also aims to minimize overcrowding in public junior high schools. Overcrowding leads to classroom congestion. Hamilton (2017) said that these congestions prevent students from concentrating on the lessons and can negatively affect students and teachers. Meanwhile, Chen (2020) contended that reducing the class size would increase overall learner accomplishment, specifically for fresher, underprivileged youngsters. Uytico (2018) reported that classroom congestion is one of the problems of DepEd, specifically in the local setting of the Eastern Visayas Region. Mateo (2019) reported that the said region consists of 96 ESC-participating Junior High Schools, and 29,548 students were grantees for the school year 2019-2020, bringing the total amount to 264,900,151.01.

The ESC program has been established for more than 30 years, but there needs to be more research on the extent of the implementation of its program and its impact on the grantees. Furthermore, Abiva (2016) attested that no available studies are linked to ESC, causing the dearth of its literature. This scarcity of data makes it difficult for DepEd to trace the progress of the recipient’s schools, making it impossible for policymakers to strengthen the program (Lucero, 1992). The recertification assessment conducted by the PEAC was limited to the school level only, and there were no further studies on the extent of its success. Thus, Velez and Paternos (2011) recommended that DepEd should monitor and evaluate the ESC so that legislators, scholars, and shareholders can determine the ESC’s usefulness. Likewise, to improve its program. There is an urgent need for an extensive and comprehensive analysis survey of the implementation of the ESC-participating schools in Region VIII to evaluate their program, probing that government funds should be spent judiciously and guiding policymakers in their planning process.

Therefore, this study sought to understand the status of the recipient schools that implemented the ESC program to see the fruits of progress, hard work, and cooperation that the public-private alliance consented to. This study considered the number of slots, recertification status, teacher qualification, enrollment rate, and grantees' academic performance. It also investigated the status of curriculum, facilities, administration, school budget, student services, and teachers. The study extracted data that pointed out how ESC-participating schools responded to the government's call to provide quality education and, in turn, served as an advent of subsequent related literature that tackled the performance of participating schools. Guided by the conviction and compelling reason to provide an in-depth analysis of ESC-participating schools of Region VIII, this study assessed the ESC-participating schools. It explored the potential problems of the program, how they are addressed, and the participants' recommendations to improve the ESC program. This may serve as a guide towards designing policy recommendations that enhance the program.

Research Questions

This study ascertained the status of the ESC-participating schools in Region VIII, as reported by the administrators and teachers. Specifically, the study explored to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the status of the demographic profile of the ESC-participating schools in terms of the following?
 - 1.1. Number of slots for Grade 7 (School Year (SY) 2020-2021)
 - 1.2. (Re) Certification Assessment Status
 - 1.3. Teacher Qualification
 - 1.4. Number of Enrollment (SY 2020-2021)
 - 1.5. Academic Performance of the ESC Grantees (MPS SY 2019-2020)
2. What is the status of the ESC-participating schools in Region VIII, as reported by the teachers and school administrators in terms of the following?
 - 2.1. Curriculum
 - 2.2. Facilities
 - 2.3. Administration
 - 2.4. School Budget
 - 2.5. Student Services
 - 2.6. Teachers
3. What are the problems encountered by the schools in the implementation of the ESC program as experienced by the administrators and teachers, and how do they address those problems?
4. What are the recommendations suggested by the administrators and teachers to improve the program?

Literature Review

Education Service Contracting in the Philippines

The Government Assistance for Students and Teachers in Private Education (GASTPE) program, where ESC belongs, is a demonstration of the government's commitment to keeping up the feasibility of private learning institutions as partners in the delivery of quality primary education (DepEd Order No.26, s. 2014). This implementation is to bridge the supply breaches like schoolrooms, schoolbooks, PCs, research laboratories, and other institute amenities that the public sector must provide for (DepEd Order No. 86, s. 2009). It has arisen as a response to the massive needs of the entire Philippine populace. During his talk at the PhilEd Conference, Mateo (2019) explained that they revised the name of the Government Assistance for Students and Teachers in Private Education (GASTPE) program to Government Assistance and Subsidies (GAS) because E-GASTPE Law (RA No. 8545) expanded the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 (RA No. 10533).

PEAC was in authority for conducting orientation conferences, constant accreditation of ESC participating schools, assessment, handling, submission of billings, and monitoring of the ESC beneficiaries (GASTPE-PAO, 2018). There are guidelines set by the DepEd and PEAC for private schools to qualify as beneficiaries. A school may qualify for the ESC program as long as it has complied with the guidelines. It must not have high cases of low NCAE performance, high dropout rates, congested classrooms, and inadequate support facilities.

Using the (Re) Certification Assessment Instrument (CAI), PEAC will evaluate the schools to ensure that they have complied with DepEd's standards. This evaluation tool will assist the ESC schools in determining their strengths and capacities. Thus, becoming a more operative learning institute ensures quality, which is the main objective of the scheme. Hence, a certified school is obliged to conform to DepEd policies. It has to meet the minimum requirements prescribed by the PEAC National Secretariat (NS) ESC Certification Unit.

Per DepEd Order No. 18, s. 2016, slot allocation is based on whether the ESC-participating school received Grade 7 ESC slots equal to its actual number of Grade 7 ESC grantees in the preceding school year (referred to as its fixed slot allocation). It was still in good standing in terms of the program and utilized its allocated slots up to capacity. In terms of the school's good standing, it should satisfactorily pass the latest certification/recertification, have no detrimental discoveries during the monitoring visit, and be liable to sanctions or penalties (Llego, 2016). DepEd Office of Planning Service (OPS) data on the unavailability of public junior high school classrooms, seats in cities and municipalities across the country, and the participating school's accreditation or certification rating also serve as bases. Moreover, the school's first program participation is allocated with "a maximum of fifty fixed Grade 7 slots". The added slots are given if the approved GASTPE budget for the school year is enough, if there is "congestion in public secondary schools in the place it is located, and if it has secured the ESC certification rating."

In terms of accreditation or certification, the school is given a maximum of thirty additional incentive slots for Level I as endorsed by the Federation of Accrediting Agencies of the Philippines (FAAP). In Level II accreditation of any member in the said federation, a school is awarded "a maximum of sixty additional incentive slots." "If the school rates above the mandated standard (3.00 and above), it will receive a maximum of thirty additional incentive slots".

In selecting the grantees, graduates of public elementary schools preferred to be qualified for ESC subsidies must undertake an evaluation for selection conducted by the committees of the school of ESC-participating schools they have preferred to apply to. The school principal, with the committee, will be accountable for the records of applicant-grantees based on need, considering the school's limited number of slots. The principal is responsible for orienting grantees and their parents/guardians about ESC program policies. There should be an attendance form where parents or guardians affix their signatures as proof that they have conducted the orientation. Along with the school event, ESC, as "a government program enacted under RA 8545 or the GASTPE Law, must be clearly emphasized and expounded to the grantees".

In 2009, approximately 9 percent of the 6.5 million high school learners were granted ESC. It continues to increase wherein the SY 2017-2018, the number of grants reached 9.6 billion, serving 1,036,891 grantees of the 3,442 private schools in the country (PEAC NS, 2019), which corresponds to 35.8 percent of 1.3 million students in private high schools. Patrinos, Barrera-Osorio, and Guáqueta (2009) view ESC as a medium to provide promoting and "making quality education available for all Filipino junior high school students." Private and public schools have complementary roles, as acknowledged by ESC (Saguin, 2019). ESC is a strategy considered an "education service delivery, entailing a model of public-finance/private provision" (LaRocque, 2011). Through this, the government enters into a contract with private counterparts that will enable qualified students to enroll in private institutions without intense hesitations and the burden of high tuition fees.

The school's quality has improved due to the ESC program. Public high schools were relieved from congestion because of the said program. The ESC program sustained the financial capability of private schools. It is because the program is subsidizing "more than one-third of its enrolment in private junior high schools." Public secondary education overall costs were also kept in check by the program. Furthermore, households were encouraged by the program to spend on education (Philippines Private Provision, Public Purpose: A Review of the Government's ESC Program, 2011; Jimenez et al., 2011). The private schools must see to it that they conform to the guidelines required to continue their operations. This study emphasizes some areas of operations for analysis. These include the curriculum, facilities, administration, school budget, student services, and teachers.

Challenges faced by the ESC in the Philippines

Soriano (2012) conducted a study on ESC in the Philippines entitled "Assessing Public-Private Partnership in Education." Findings showed that GASTPE decongested the public education system, but it has failed to "reach out to the poorest of the poor as" opposed to what it has envisioned. Such a study argued that the parents gained additional expenses because the tuition fees have grown substantially due to the need for expensive textbooks, school uniforms, and materials that reach beyond their monetary budgets. Parallel to this claim, it pointed out that the government must increase the ESC subsidy to answer this issue.

Saguin (2019) revealed a misguided distribution of ESC slots due to the absence of evidence on the degree of overcrowding in public secondary schools. It also lacks the procedural instruments intended for identifying their capacities. Then, it summed up the idea that ESC is far from achieving its objectives of "decongesting the public education system and providing access to poor but deserving students."

Advantages of having ESC in the Philippines

Abiva (2016) determined both the facilitating and impeding reasons as they implemented the GASTPE program and its influence on the schools that participated in this program. It was found that the program enhanced the quality of the school, stabilized the school financially, school standards, cost-effectiveness, teachers' long tenure, and marginalized students' accessibility to secondary education. Unfortunately, the principal's denial in pronouncing "aisle" learners, parents who are not supportive, privileged rich grantees instead of the underprivileged candidates, a remoteness of home from school, deficiency of monetary funds to pay other school expenses, lesser improvement in the program delivery services, and subsidy amount are the preventing factors towards the success of ESC's vision for the entire educational system. Besides, other aspects that impact the quality and accessibility of education are the income of the family, the degree of the parent's educational attainment, and socio-cultural. Thus, they have barred the fulfillment of the objective of the program (Jennifer, 2013).

Velez et al. (2011) also administered a study on the Philippines' public-private provision and revealed that the country gained very low student test scores. However, the test scores specified the potential of the private schools in improving the outcomes of learning because the raw distinction "between private and public schools is significant even after regulating student's backgrounds and other notable differences." The private school's findings were still consistent as having high test scores, and it was discovered that "students in private schools improved their scores." Hereby affecting the "academic test scores of the Philippines in their entirety." Furthermore, the study suggested that ESC intensifies a widespread range of learners and "schools instead of establishing new schools or classrooms." Unfortunately, the study revealed that disbursements of funds to beneficiaries' schools are frequently late, and various institutes "remain unpaid at the end of the school year."

Moreover, past studies concentrated entirely on how advantageous private education is over public education (Jimenez et al., 1995), which is constant with the impression that private schools bid an education that is better in its quality. However, there is growing indication that ESC has not extended its preferred aim of decongesting the public secondary education system. Based on the representation of decongestion, inequalities are present because other regions have received more than those who really need it

(Jimenez, 2011). From thence, there is a call to maintain equilibrium depending on what is prescribed under the GASTPE law so that all qualified learners are privileged to have such an opportunity to escape poverty and other socio-economic factors. On the other hand, preliminary organizational procedures wanted to provide the ESC program to poor but deserving students, too. However, the current findings of the COA have shown that the ESC scheme/program has failed to cater to its ideal beneficiaries. Consequently, it has not prioritized underprivileged students (Philippine Commission on Audit, 2018). From the rates concerned, the rate achievement of ESC grantees is about 78%, which fell lower than the average rate in the national rating of about 83% in 2015 (CPBRD, 2014). Hence, the governing system failed to ensure the program's maximum gains.

Behind its limitations, the status of ESC participating schools was moderately good in terms of physical facilities, and they accurately complied with the qualities of an ideal ESC school (Lucero, 1992). Hence, learning is fostered in the establishment of tangible resources together with the cognitive success of the schools involved.

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a qualitative design, particularly a multiple-case study research design. The researcher first describes the demographic profile of the ESC participating schools, followed by an in-depth analysis of the status of curriculum, facilities, school budget, administration, student services, and teachers. Afterward, a thematic analysis (Braun & Clark) was used to analyze the problems in the program's implementation, how they resolved them, and the suggestions recommended by the participants to improve the program.

Participants

This study was conducted in Region VIII's twelve ESC-participating schools. The participants were twelve (12) administrators and twenty-four (24) teachers who worked for at least three years during the school year 2020-2021. The total population was considered for a qualitative research design.

Instrument

The researcher utilized an Interview Guide to gather data from the participants. The interview guide was constructed based on the problems' statements. The first part dealt with the status of the demographic profile of ESC-participating schools. This comprised the questions on the number of slots of Grade 7 in SY 2020-2021, recertification assessment rating, teacher qualification, the enrollment rate in SY 2020-2021, and academic performance of ESC Grade 10 grantees based on the mean percentage score (MPS) in the SY 2019-2020. The first part was intended for administrators only. Meanwhile, the second part emphasized the status of the ESC-participating schools in Region VIII, as reported by the administrators and teachers. It comprised questions about curriculum, facilities, administration, school budget, student services, and teachers. The third part consisted of questions on the problems encountered by the school in implementing the ESC program, how they addressed those problems, and suggested recommendations to improve the program. Moreover, open-ended questions allowed participants to use comprehensive and varied perspectives. Participants consented to recording the entire interview session to capture all the information the informants gave and, simultaneously, to validate the authenticity of the data for the transcription.

Procedure

Data was collected through semi-structured interviews and collection of documents. There were two interview protocols, particularly for administrators and teachers. The interview lasted more or less than thirty minutes and was conducted in their respective schools for the Leyte and Southern Leyte provinces. In contrast, the rest of the schools in other provinces conducted cellular phone interviews. Both interviews were audio/phone recorded. The researcher provided notes to record during the interview. A post-interview was conducted for member checking to allow the participants to validate, change, and enhance their responses.

Data Analysis

The questions were answered by looking at the commonalities and variances between its cases and defining exactly how to answer questions, respectively, with the data received (Yuksel, 2010). This data analysis method allowed the researcher to identify commonly recognized patterns and relationships that answer the study's research questions meaningfully. Specifically, a table was created to summarize, organize, and analyze to form a theme of each case. Following Braun and Clarke (2013), the audio interviews were first transcribed verbatim into a Microsoft Word (MS Word) document. Verbal responses, direct quotes, and participant examples were then used to provide and ensure accuracy. However, for purposely using grammar correctly, the text was edited when quoting their verbatim responses, but keeping its thought and content mindfully. Second was reading and familiarization; Third was coding the data's essential features; fourth was reviewing the themes. Fifth, determine the significance of the themes, and sixth, report the findings.

The process allows the researcher to gain acquaintance and absorption for an in-depth data examination. Through this, the researcher obtained the participants' information about the status of the demographic profile of the ESC-participating schools, viewpoints on the schools' status in terms of curriculum, facilities, administration, school budget, student services, and teachers' problems encountered

while implementing the program, how they resolved the problems and suggested recommendations to improve the program.

Moreover, this study followed the multiple-case design, where the data was organized, summarized, and analyzed based on the participant's responses, thus utilizing interviews and documents. The constant comparative method using the within-case analysis and cross-case synthesis allowed the researcher to construct a final analysis within each case. In this study, the researcher's comparison within and between cases ultimately led to a deeper understanding of the status of the ESC-participating schools in Region VIII.

Ethical Considerations

To address various concerns in preserving the privacy and security of the respondents, the researcher followed integrity and supported the Data Privacy Law and kept their identities and information discreet.

The researcher presented and discussed the informed consent and assent to the respondents before the conduct of the study to give them the freedom to decline their participation. To assure them of their privacy, the researcher followed these steps: (1) distinguishing and coding of data; (2) no particular identifying information or mark in the survey questionnaire or the computer; (3) a secure storage for the data throughout the study; (4) destroying of information after use.

Confidentiality was maintained throughout the research to protect participants' right to privacy. The researcher masked the identities of both schools and participants by using code on all data files and documents.

Results and Discussion

This section provides the results of the study. First, it presents case descriptions of the status of the demographic profile of each school based on its number of slots for Grade 7 in the SY 2020-2021, (re) certification assessment, teacher qualification, the number of enrollments, and the academic performance of the ESC grantees based on the MPS of the SY 2019-2020. Second, it provides the results of the second research question on the status of the ESC-participating schools in terms of curriculum, facilities, administration, school budget, student services, and teachers. The last part presents the results of the third research question on the problems encountered by the identified schools in the implementation of the program, how they addressed their problems, and the recommendations suggested by the participants to improve the program. Within each result, the researcher presents a comprehensive analysis of each case by the school as reported by the administrators and teachers; subsequently, the researcher provides a cross-case comparison of all the twelve schools in each area, which synthesizes the individual case analyses for each research question. A summary table was presented to summarize each response.

The case study of the ESC-participating schools is presented according to the statement of the problem.

Table 1. Status of the Demographic Profile of the ESC-Participating Schools

<i>ESC Schools</i>	<i>Number of slots (Gr7 SY 2020-2021)</i>	<i>(Re) Certification Assessment Status</i>	<i>Teacher Qualification</i>	<i>Number of Enrolment (SY 2020-2021)</i>	<i>Mean Percentage Score (MPS) Gr10 SY 2019-2020</i>
School A	250	2.7	All Licensed	1,149	87%
School B	139	2	Licensed -14 Non-Licensed-1	437	61.02%
School C	255	2	Licensed -19 Non-Licensed-8	5,260	81.55%
School D	94	3.37	Licensed -21 Non-Licensed-7	413	77%
School E	80	3.1	Licensed -10 Non-Licensed-1	295	90%
School F	(202).	PAASCU-accredited Level II	All Licensed	1,001	66.95%
School G	150	2.94	All Licensed	2,383	88.32%
School H	15	1	Licensed- 4 Non-Licensed-1	101	84.13%
School I	100	2.6	Licensed- 14 Non-Licensed-14	490	81.84%
School J	111	3.19	Licensed-13 Non-Licensed-1	398	82.27%
School K	150	PAASCU-accredited Level III	All Licensed	591	85.94%
School L	175	3.20	Licensed-29 Non-Licensed-3	1,002	83.5%

Table 1 presents the status of the demographic profile of the selected ESC-participating schools in Region VIII. The data revealed that the schools have various slots for Grade 7 for the SY 2020-2021. The highest number of slots allocated was 255, followed by 250, and

the lowest number of slots allocated was 15. It is to be noted that the fixed slots are 50. Additional incentive slots will be given to schools with Level 1 accreditation by FAAP, and a maximum of sixty additional incentive slots for Level II accreditation. If the school rating is above the mandated standard (3.00 and above), it will receive a maximum of thirty additional incentive slots. Thus, the schools with over 50 slots were already awarded the other incentive slots. Two PAASCU-accredited schools were allocated 202 slots and 150 slots, respectively, based on the previous enrollment.

The recertification assessment status varied from each other because the (re) certification assessment instrument (CAI) for certification was revised. Before 2019, PEAC used the old version of the CAI to certify the schools with a different qualitative description. The revised version of CAI has another way of rating and interpreting. The highest rating before the CAI 2018 was 3.37, described as “Above Standards,” while the lowest was 2.6, “Within the Standard.” Subsequently, the highest rating obtained when the CAI 2018 was administered for (re) certification was 2.0. This could mean that the school presented partial compliance, and the revisit will be after three years. The lowest rating was 1, which means there was no evidence of compliance but just a plan of action for compliance.

The teacher’s qualifications differed in some schools. Some schools accept licensed teachers only, while others accept licensed and non-licensed teachers. The highest number of licensed teachers were in Schools A, G, and K because all teachers were certified, and the secondary department was composed of approximately more or less than twenty teachers. The highest number of unlicensed teachers was in School I. The number of licensed and unlicensed teachers was the same (14 licensed; 14 unlicensed). School J had the lowest number of unlicensed teachers, with only one unlicensed teacher. Only those licensed teachers can avail themselves of the Teachers Salary Subsidy (TSS).

Specifically, all schools are affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. One of the effects of the pandemic was the number of enrollments. Enrollment in all schools decreased in different percentages. The highest recorded decrease was about 28%, while the lowest was 3.19%. The schools also differ in the number of enrollments. The highest enrolment comprised 5,260 students and 2,383 students in the SY 2020-2021. The lowest enrolment was composed of 101 students. The most increased enrolments were in the schools in the cities, while those with fewer were in the barangays. This is reasonable because of the population in the towns compared to the barangays.

The academic performance of the grantees is based on the Mean Percentage Score (MPS), which was taken from the school year 2019-2020. The highest MPS was in School E, with 90%, which means “Mastery is closely Approximate.” It was followed by School A, with 87% having the same mastery level. The lowest MPS was in School B, with 61.02% described as “Moving Towards Mastery” level.

Table 2. Status of the ESC-participating schools of curriculum, facilities, administration, school budget, student services, and teachers

	Curriculum	Facilities	Administration	School Budget	Student Services	Teachers
E	DepEd Compliant;	-Accessible	collaborative	-budget	-online and	-Teacher’s
S	K-12 standard-		administration	transparency	offline mode	Satisfaction
C	based curriculum	-Technologically-enhanced	democratic	-budgetary	-Status of	-Fast Turn-
S	Alignment of the	•Status of facilities	administration	allocation,	student	over
C	curriculum with the	(70-100% adequate,	potentially-based	-sustainability of	services (50-	-status of
H	school’s vision and	accessible, and	administration	the budget	100%	teaching
O	mission	available			assurance of	profession
O			Status of the	-status of the	delivery	(50%-100%)
L	Level of curriculum		principal’s	sustainability of		
S	implementation		management skill	the budget (50-		
	(70-100%		(80-100%)	100% due to the		
	implemented			ESC subsidy		

Legend: 9-10 (90-100%) Very High, 7-8(70-80%)High, 5-6(50-60%)Average, 3-4 (30- 40%) Low, 0-2 (0-29%) Very low

Through the within-case analysis and cross-case synthesis, using the thematic approach of Braun and Clarke, ten (10) themes were formulated, such as Curriculum are Dep-Ed Compliant, Aligned with Vision-Mission, Technologically Enhanced Facilities, Collaborative, Democratic, and Potentially based Administrators, Budget Transparency, Budgetary Allocation, and Sustainability of the Budget, Adaptation of Online-Offline Student Services, and Teacher’s Satisfaction and Fast Turnover.

The ESC-participating schools fully comply with the DepEd Minimum Quality Standards on implementing the K to 12 Curriculum for secondary educational institutions (2018-19, CAI, 2). They expressly declared: “We follow what the DepEd mandates” (A7, L18), “We adapted the curriculum of ESC set by DepEd” (T11, L5-6), and “We implemented following the rules and memo of the DepEd” (T12, L5).

Some statements from the participants were:

The curriculum implementation is exemplary because, in addition to following the DepEd curriculum, we are ensuring that we also meet our school's vision and mission. That is why we are doing well in implementing the curriculum (T1, L21-23).

We have the choice of how we implement the curriculum, for example, the additional subject- Christian Living since this is a Catholic school focusing on prayer, worship, and morals, and we have different activities integrated into our curriculum (T23, L5-8).

Our implementation is very satisfactory because the JHS department has responded positively to the demands of the DepEd in its desire to deliver quality learning across the felt needs of our learners (A7, L19-22).

The instructional program is grounded in the school's mission and expectations for student learning (2018-19, CAI, 6). They have also added Christian Living to their curriculum by which the school integrates its core values and charism. Each perceived that this curriculum made them different from the other schools. While the teachers accredited their high level of status in the curriculum implementation, two administrators admitted that challenges are common in the fast turnover of teachers that would slightly affect the curriculum implementation. However, they would maintain the standards despite the turnover. That is why schools are training their teachers from time to time. The quantitative rating was about 70-100%, meaning the curriculum was highly implemented.

The second area evaluated was the status of the facilities. Based on the data, the facilities are adequate, accessible or available, and technologically enhanced. One participant commented: "I think when it comes to facilities, very accessible and adequate; we lack nothing" (T16, L17). Some comments were:

There are things we need to improve, but I would say that it is 10/10 because when my co-teachers visit here, they applaud the facilities we have, and the maintenance is excellent. We ensure that the facilities and equipment in that particular laboratory are sound and complete (T21, L22-26).

That is 95% because we have complete facilities here. We have a science laboratory, speech laboratory, and computer laboratory. We have good facilities for better instruction of our students to facilitate learning easier (T23, L26-29).

Adequacy of facilities measures whether the school has enough facilities and is suitable in quality and quantity. Availability of facilities measures the school facilities if they are accessible and ready for use. Technologically enhanced facilities measure innovative facilities. Most administrators and teachers were proud of their facilities, such as speech lab, computer lab, and science lab, to mention a few used to facilitate better learning. The documents in the recertification assessment validated their responses, and most of the schools were equipped with the required facilities. While they boasted of the adequateness and accessibility of their facilities, the participants were open to more improvement. Furthermore, all ESC schools boosted the use of technology in their instruction. However, there was a problem with a poor internet connection.

The schools, though, in financial constraints, do all they can to update their facilities. Although some find it hard, they ensure the facilities are all functional. To ensure this, some schools procured high-quality equipment and materials. Lastly, each participant accepted the limitations they have concerning their facilities. Still, they took pride in the equipment they have as a means of delivering powerful instruction and developing the well-being of their clients. Also, they believed that having good facilities promotes quality learning. The equivalent quantitative rating was about 70-100%, meaning the ESC schools highly regarded their facilities.

Regarding the status of their administration, administrators and teachers had a different set of questions. The focus was to evaluate how the school principal manages the school. It was to assess if the school had an administration, particularly a principal, that promotes mutual, collaborative, and philosophical relationships with its stakeholders and the community that is conducive to quality student learning (2018-19, CAI, 22) and if there are a positive culture and harmonious relationships among the members of the school community. Nevertheless, the data was not limited to the criterion set by experts. It goes beyond what was experienced and observed by the participants. Since the administrator was also a participant, they looked carefully at what kind of principal they were, which would reflect what type of administration the school had.

Data reveals the types of administration present in an ESC school, that is, collaborative administration (CA), democratic administration (DA), and potentially based administration (PBA). A collaborative administration involves teachers and staff communicating with each other and working together to achieve the vision and mission of the school as an institution. They remarked, "For her management, I will give ten given 1 to 10 because she always collaborates" (T9, 28-29). Also, another said that: "Given 1 to 10, I rate 9 for her because she is that good" (T10, L17-18). Principals have learned that engaging the entire school staff in making decisions results in more commitment to school reform initiatives (Buckner, 2020). A democratic administration allows freedom of expression, thought, and collective decision-making and promotes a creative environment, which leads to progress. A potentially based administration governs by permitting individuals to grow in their fields and develop their capacity to cultivate and transfer learning in an innovative and self-governing way.

Some statements to support this claim are the following:

Our school principal is very approachable and concerned with us. I feel that we are just one family. There is no such thing as superiors or inferiors, but we are all equal (T16, L22-24).

Our school principal is doing her best to achieve the school's objectives and goals through seminars and training, especially for the new teachers (T21, L21-22).

They are coaches; they guide us in growing personally and even spiritually to grow professionally. From time to time, every month, we have this gathering to talk about our strengths and weaknesses in every department or office (T23, L35-37).

While all schools manifest a democratic, collaborative, and potential-based type of administration, participants experienced and exhibited it in varying situations. Some articulated it clearly, while others expressed it vaguely. Likewise, some teachers mentioned motivation as a critical factor in working more than salaries. Teachers had a more favorable taste for the democratic way of administration. Freedom of expression and being listened to in their concerns encourage them to work to promote the welfare of the school. A sense of ownership is the best way to drive teachers to work with innovation, and according to Brewster and Larson (1992), decentralized power “can be the recipe for efficient elicitation.” Also, Daisyme (2019) affirmed that when employees feel “a sense of ownership, they are likely to” do their best. This right gives them a sense of autonomy, which Daisyme (2019) calls it; they have skin in the game. Therefore, they appreciate it when administrators acknowledge their potential. They recognized that it is one way of growing professionally. Being open to ideas and suggestions is also a manifestation of having a democratic administration where everybody is permitted to speak up on behalf of the teachers. It was also potential-based because one can develop one's potential by allowing one to leave one's comfort zone. More likely, one prefers not to say anything to avoid the situation, give up, or quit. Franklin (2019) stated that one of the reasons for staying silent is to maintain the status quo. Therefore, for him, when one learns to speak up, they create an opportunity for things to change. So, to have an administration where everyone is welcome to speak up, there could be a tremendous achievement of whatever the school is planning.

Teachers from all schools have very high regard for the managerial skills of their principal. Their support and motivations influenced their working conditions. Most of the teachers quantitatively raised the status of the administration from high to a very high level from 80-100%. All teachers felt that the administration shared the same values but expressed them in different ways that were comfortable for them; however, challenges of various kinds strengthened the administrators. On the other hand, administrators were grateful for the many benefits they enjoyed. Not to mention monetary profit, they equally acknowledged the seminars/webinars, training, and workshops attended as part of their supervisory growth. Likewise, their supportive communities inspire them to work more for the welfare of their clients and the community. According to the principal: “I do everything. I do my best for the good of the students, the school, and my community” (A4, L36-37). However, the challenges sometimes haunted them, yet they learned to cope. Some challenges they shared were financial constraints, lack of personnel, the demands of the K-12 curriculum, qualifications, fast turnover, millennial teachers, and distance learning. Nonetheless, they were able to surpass those challenges.

Another area of operation evaluated was the school budget. The formulated theme was budget transparency, allocation, and sustainability of the budget. Budget transparency is the disclosure of all pertinent financial data properly and organized. The budgetary allocation is the amount of finance designated to each expenditure line. It is an essential element of an annual financial plan or budget. Sustainability of funding means that the school budget is stable and can withstand and continue the operation in any condition. While teachers appreciated the well-allocated budget: “The school is well budgeted in terms of the need of the school. Given 1 to 10, it is around 8.5 or 85% based on my observation, some factors need more budget” (T20, L26-27), some experienced dissatisfaction due to its lack of transparency; on account of the interview responses, most teachers did not know how the fund flows. One participant commented, “We do not know the flow 100% of the school budgeting” (T3, L57). Others said that “if the scale is 1 to 5 for the status of the school budget, she will rate it two (2) because of the lack of transparency” (T3, L65), while some say:

As teachers, we are not involved in the school's budgeting matters. So, we did not discuss it with teachers. We do not talk about the budget. It is a private matter (T5, 28-29, 33-34).

Regarding the budget, sister, I am still determining the budget proposal. I need an idea about funding (T6, L28, 30-31).

Nevertheless, they were satisfied with the allocation because it is visible on the facilities and equipment. One participant commented:

I do not know how the school budget works, but they allocated the money well because it can be seen in the facilities and campus beautification. I am curious how they came up with the budget proposal (T16, L28-31).

However, statements between administrators and teachers needed to be more consistent. For instance, the administrators recounted that they disclosed the school budget during orientation, but the teachers conveyed that the administration did not present it during orientation. Some teachers suggested that the school be transparent with the budget and involve teachers in budget planning. Transparency is beneficial for administrators so that together, they can build trust. The logic of transparency is when we remove the mystery; according to Galias (n.d.), it can help everyone see why the school does what it does. When the school is clear about its goals and direction, it can inspire the stakeholders and will surely open the opportunity for active participation and support. That way, they can prioritize what and how to allocate the budget equitably. Each participant acknowledged that the COVID-19 pandemic added to the financial sustainability risk. This is due to the decrease in enrollment. They all said that “we are decreasing this year due to the pandemic.”

After all, we have limited financial resources, especially during this pandemic when enrolment has decreased (A11, L81-84).

However, the school found ways to sustain its operation and survive despite the crisis. The sustainability of the school budget is somewhat “9/10” (A9, L64). They somehow acknowledged the government assistance, the ESC subsidy, as the chief source of their survival, and it added to the stability and sustainability of their continued operation with or without the pandemic. Some recognize that ESC is part of the life of private schools. As they recounted, it is really of great help to the teachers, students, parents, and the school. One participant said:

We had only 200 students before the ESC, but we have increased because of it. It helps the school financially. When we made the budget, we allotted 10-15% for bad debts, but now, with the ESC Fund, only 3-5% is allocated (A10, L141-143).

During the 2020-2021 school year, they drastically changed how it delivered student services. The pandemic dramatically shifted the educational system, affecting student services. Nevertheless, the resiliency of the ESC-participating schools through the Learning Continuity Plan (LCP) enables them to deliver student services in a different mode. During the interview, the participants were emotional when asked about the status of their student services. They shared that the COVID-19 pandemic restricted face-to-face encounters with students. It eventually limits their services for academic and non-academic aspects. Problems arise within the administration, teachers, parents, students, and the school. The ESC schools adopted online/virtual modality and offline modality.

The school’s vision and mission guide the implementation of our LCP, so although there is no physical contact with the students, our services, for example, guidance, conduct virtual counseling. If there is a problematic student, we conduct virtual counseling. In our library, we also have the so-called e-library, wherein the librarian in charge assists with textbooks if students request them, especially those who have no textbooks (A3, L70-76).

The guidance office is functioning, the library is open, and the campus ministry offers virtual services. Their canteen still operates. Some comments were:

Regarding spirituality, our campus ministry services sister is still conducting holy masses virtually, so students are invited to attend. So, continue gihapon ang campus ministry services, guidance counseling online, and school canteen though close, but they also have services (A3, L77-80).

We do have to reach out to students with our guidance, campus ministry, and all those services for student services (T6, L37-38).

Despite the difficult situations, administrators and teachers in all schools shared that they assured that learning continues. Based on the interview results, all participants experienced stressful moments, but they are doing their best to cater to the needs of the students. Some administrators reported that they go beyond their services, and the school has been outsourcing to address these needs. Moreover, the school continues to serve. Guidance counseling is available online and offline. Campus ministry services like holy mass and religious activities continue virtually. Library Instructional Media Center, which includes digital and printed articles, is accessible. Laboratories like science laboratories (biology, chemistry, physics, computer laboratories, and TLE laboratories are functional. They conducted student activity programs like academic and non-academic activities online. Health services like medical services and dental services are open to their clients. The services in the registrar are also accessible online and offline.

As much as the school wanted to bring out the best and quality services, the pandemic limited them, and they encountered problems such as poor internet connectivity. Some also referred to hostile parents, sudden lockdowns, ECQ protocols, and the rising number of COVID-19-positive cases in their places. Some students lacked interest in the activities conducted by the school. However, the school addressed these emerging issues one at a time. It is their goal that its operation would continue even amid all uncertainties. The creativity and initiative of each personnel made the new standard easier to deal with, as they shared positively. Despite all these challenges, ESC schools remain positive and hopeful. By bringing these services to their client's homes, teachers and administrators ensure they do their best despite the hardships, pressures, and stress. Somehow, they were able to manage it all. Their lowest rating for their student services was about 5/10, equivalent to 50% at an average level, and the highest was 100%. The range is at the middle-level (a reference to the Likert scale), which means that services were delivered well at the intermediate level. More so, the schools assured me that they would not compromise their competencies even with this new way of education. They stated that:

During this pandemic, we can still provide students with information about school activities online. We try to be accessible to students; if they cannot access us, we find other ways to relay the information (T19, L27-29).

We still have virtual monitoring on one video or mobile call. This way, we can connect and ask the students if they need help studying. We are still exploring ways to extend our support to the students. We ensure that we carry out our services through our online conferences, such as mental wellness- how to cope with the demands of everything (T24, L47-52).

The last area evaluated in this research was the status of teachers in an ESC school. During data analysis, the themes formulated were teacher satisfaction and fast turnover. Teachers were satisfied with the school's training and seminars/webinars for their professional growth. Some of them mentioned the Professional Learning Community (PLC), which allows teachers to share and talk about growing in their profession as teachers. The In-service Training (INSET) conducted by the PEAC was their favorite haven for learning techniques and strategies to improve their performance. Some say:

I was happy and contented because the school helps us grow professionally. They honed our skills, morality, and spirituality (T23,

L78-80).

All teachers are required, and after each demo, each teacher will give feedback on areas to improve and strengths. It is also a professional learning community (PLC) where we exchange ideas on how to follow the RVM pedagogy. Each personnel member is tasked with presenting a video clip for reflection and sharing. Since its advent, we have decided to have an advent recollection and confession with our parish priest (A10, L109-117).

I am also challenged to develop my professional skills and personal faith because there are activities we will not find in other schools, like retreats, recollections, and daily hour adoration. So now and then, we are reminded to reflect, to immerse into a deep, you know, a more significant responsibility not just to teach the topic but also to teach with the integration of the lesson of the values found in the school in the society, and the teachings of Jesus (T20, L82-87).

Another factor is spiritual growth. Durham (2020) states that this is about reaching out to and connecting with one's inner soul to create harmony in one's life. It also develops one's feelings of inner power and strength. It will lead to living a happier life and becoming more responsible for their actions. The teachers appreciated the religious activities in school that developed their spirituality and boosted their morale. Recollections, annual retreats, holy rosary, holy mass, and adoration were some of the religious activities they mentioned as one way of developing their faith.

With all these personal developments, the teachers were personally satisfied with the program and were grateful to the administrators for providing for their spiritual life aside from their financial needs. Personal satisfaction is significant when working in an organization because when one feels self-motivated, contented, and fulfilled with one's actions, one will probably be successful. The teachers in the ESC-participating school admitted that they were personally satisfied. They are happy being in the private school because they are intellectually and spiritually shaped. However, most, if not all, of them said that salary is low. So even if they are satisfied, one teacher shared that the administration cannot stop those teachers who like to transfer to public schools where the salary is higher than private schools. That is why all of them acknowledged the Teacher's Salary Subsidy (TSS) as a great help to cover their financial needs, and they all clamored that TSS and salary would increase. One teacher said that increasing TSS would lessen the fast turnover in private schools. Nonetheless, teachers maintain a higher status in their teaching profession in an ESC school despite the low salary.

The TSS covers what needs to be added to our salary. As I said, our compensation must be revised to cover all our needs. Some of us have families, so our needs have changed as well. So, the TSS is really of great help. We are all happy when it comes. The program is essential in helping us cope financially (T23, L101-104).

The teachers accepted the challenges they encountered as a learning process. Consequently, they were able to resolve those conflicts. They further shared that they need help with the new system of education, where face-to-face interaction is not allowed. However, their dedication and passion inspired them to work 24/7 to serve their students. Furthermore, participants were grateful because there was no retrenchment in their workplace.

Though our enrolment has decreased, the most beautiful part is that the school did not have retrenchment. We keep the same status of the school. Though the school struggled with finances, everybody stayed intact. So it was a big thing for us also, considering that most, if not all, private schools have their retrenchment, but here we are all intact. To God be the glory (A11, L134-138).

Table 3. Summary of the Problems, School's Solutions, and Recommendations in the Implementation of the ESC Program

<i>Problems</i>	<i>School's Solution</i>	<i>Recommendations</i>
Delayed Grant Insufficient Subsidy Grantee's Lack of Interest and Parental Support	Refund System Scholarship Home Visitation and Orientation	Early Release of the Subsidy Increase the Subsidy Evaluation of the Impact Monitoring of the academic performance of the grantees
PEAC Re/Certification Pressures	Constant Updating of the PEAC requirements	
Complicated Online Transactions of the ESC on the Grantees Fast turnover of teachers		Creation of a System for Online Process Increase TSS Strengthen Public-Private Partnership

Problems, school solutions, and recommendations for implementing the ESC program were based on the data collected through an interview, summarized, organized, and analyzed using within-case analysis and cross-case synthesis. Six (6) themes were categorized under the problems: Delayed Grant, Insufficient Subsidy, Grantee's Lack of Interest and Parental Support, PEAC Re/Certification Pressures, Complicated Online Transactions, and Fast Turnover of Teachers. Four (4) themes were categorized under the school's solution: Refund System, Scholarship, Home Visitation and Orientation, and Constant Updating of the PEAC requirements. Seven (7) themes were categorized under recommendations: Early Release of the Subsidy, Increase of the Subsidy, Evaluation of the Impact of the ESC on the Grantees, Monitoring of the academic performance of the grantees, Creation of a System for Online Process, Increase TSS for Teachers, and Strengthen Public-Private Partnership.

Administrators and teachers expressed gratitude and appreciation for the ESC program and acknowledged it as part of a private school. However, they also conveyed the implementation's lapses, challenges, and problems. While the teachers and administrators reported various problems implementing the program, some occur daily. The first was the delayed grant. Some schools compensate for the late release by paying it first, while other schools ask parents to pay it first, and then they would be given a refund when subsidies are billed out. It was a burden to the school and the parents, especially if the former was economically unstable and lacked financial resources. The following were some sharing of the participants:

So, we look for another scholarship for them because dropouts mostly come from low-income families, and nobody provides for their other needs. We go the extra mile for slow learners to reach out to them. The school pays first for a late subsidy, so the school is overburdened with the late release of the support (A1, L112-115).

We try to find an outside source and ask for donors. If there are, we will be happy to promote the school to increase enrollment. However, right now, because of the pandemic, it is pending (A8, L94-96).

The second problem was the insufficient subsidy. It cannot cover the needs of grantees. That is why there are dropouts and transfers out. However, when the grantees decide to return the following year, it would be another problem because they cannot avail of it anymore. The policy states that transfer to another ESC-participating JHS is allowed, but when the grantee transfers to a non-ESC-participating JHS, the grant is terminated (DO, 20, s. 2017). One participant shared her sentiments: "Our main problem is that grantees transferred to other schools. We could not stop them because the reasons are sometimes valid, like family problems" (T18, L100-102). To address this problem, a participant shared:

We talk to parents, but if the reason is very valid, like the change of residence due to the parent's work, we let them go (A10, L163-164).

The third problem was the grantee's lack of interest. This issue is related to parents' lack of support for their children. These two problems are inseparable. If parents are not supportive, their students will lack interest in studying. Delgado (2019) affirmed that when parents involved themselves in teaching, their students' academic performance would improve. When parents are supportive, the students feel more motivated to learn, and their grades improve. It will also enhance teachers' performance because they will feel valued.

This problem is felt most especially by teachers who have direct contact with the grantees. Though some grantees are doing very well because they remember they are "scholars," some do not think about it and are very careless in their studies. PEAC does not use the word "scholar" to identify a student who benefits from the ESC program because the grant primarily aims "to decongest overcrowded public junior high schools." The slots allocated "are for students who would otherwise have gone to public schools," but they do not complement the grades or whatever accomplishments they have before their entrance to junior high school. Also, no maintenance ratings are required within a school year, and as long as the grantee is promoted to the next level, the grant remains in force (DO, 20, s. 2017). Thus, the school conducted home visitation, talked, and explained to parents the purpose and importance of the subsidy. Some of the sharing were:

The problem is on the part of the students; at least 5% of the grantees who are not serious about their studies think that the government subsidizes them, and even face-to-face classes are not that serious (A11, L150-152).

We conducted home visitation because when we called the parents, they would not reply, so we would go to their house to see the grantee's situation and why they needed to comply with the requirements. Thus, we found out that there are grantees who have a dysfunctional family as they live with their Lola's. Others are both parents are abroad, so nobody keeps them (A11, L169-173).

The fourth problem was PEAC Re/Certification Pressures, where tons of documents had to be prepared, and the fifth was the complicated online transactions related to billing and signature affixation. Some participants shared:

It is tasking. Working on documents was not easy. It has to undergo many processes. If we have recertification, asking the teachers to do this is too difficult because they are swamped (T1, L124-126).

This time, the challenge is the online transaction for ESC billing and all related to ESC. We are having difficulty because we do not know how to affix a signature (T15, L70-71).

By good communication and constant updating, they were able to address these problems.

The sixth problem was the fast turnover of teachers because of the low salary. One of the teachers stated that the low salary is the main reason they have only two old teachers; the rest are fresh graduates. Conversely, the teachers are grateful to the TSS because it helps them financially. That is why some participants shared some sentiments:

It would be nice if the government could add more to the TSS. At least it can, in a small way, compensate for what our counterparts in the public schools are receiving. The private schools need it (T5, L82-85).

The greatest dream I have in my life is that teachers will not receive the subsidy only once a year and that the government will provide their salaries so that they will be motivated to do better (A2, L93-95).

Thus, the school acknowledges the importance of the subsidy for its survival. The participants admitted, referring to the subsidy as “a big help for us” (A3, L118).

One of the participants, on the other hand, commented:

I have been here for quite a long time, and I am grateful to have been a beneficiary of the ESC program. As a teacher, I am enjoying my work despite the low compensation, as we know that the compensation in private schools is not that promising (T5, L59-61).

Administrators and teachers in each institution were optimistic about the ESC program, which is highly recommended to continue to help the private schools, students, parents, and teachers. They highly recommended the early release of the subsidy and increasing it for teachers and students. The reason for increasing the grant for them is to increase enrollment in private schools and allow students to avail themselves of a quality catholic education, which everybody aspires to. They also suggested increasing the TSS for teachers to minimize the fast turnover.

Other suggestions are to evaluate the impact of the ESC on the grantees, monitor their academic performance, create a systematic process for affixing signatures for billing, and minimize requirements during recertification. Additional suggestions are to include the transferees in the subsidy and elementary teachers for TSS. There must be an allowance for students and unlimited slots, and grantees must maintain a higher rating. They also suggested strengthening public-private partnerships by asking the government to help increase the salaries of private school teachers.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions are given.

It is concluded that the demographic profile of the ESC-participating schools was in good condition. However, enrollments were few because of the high tuition fees despite the subsidy.

The subsidy cannot cover all the tuition fees of the grantees.

The schools strive to maintain their status quo as ESC beneficiaries. They keep finding methods to implement the curriculum well, to have facilities conducive to learning, a pro-employee administration, a feasible budget, a student service that is open to change, and well-trained teachers.

ESC participating schools need more transparency in financial matters and have problems retaining teachers due to the low salaries.

ESC subsidy is the “lifeblood” of private schools, implying that most of their budget depends on subsidies. That is why the late release and insufficient subsidy were the number one problem they complained about. Thus, they recommended increasing the subsidies and suggesting releasing the grants as early as possible. They also complained of the grantee's lack of interest in studying.

With all its clamors, the findings from this study support the idea that the combination of a robust government support system and the operation of a school's good management is the perfect component of achieving a solid and quality education.

The unflinching support of the PEAC to private schools sustains its quality operation. It implies that the monitoring and evaluation through burdensome help regulate the schools and help maintain their standards; subsequently, all twelve ESC-participating schools remarkably managed to uphold their standards and status following the guidelines of the Department of Education.

The following recommendations were drawn out of the findings of the study.

Based on the conclusions, it is highly recommended that the ESC program would continue. However, they must increase the subsidy amount and release it as early as possible so parents and schools can recover financially.

It was suggested that there must be an increase in the salary of teachers to minimize the fast turnover.

The school must be transparent to gain more understanding from the stakeholders and to raise awareness of its financial status. Lazere (2019) points out that transparency is a key to education equity and better school budgets. He further explains that when the stakeholders are involved with the budget, they will fully understand it and probably contribute to their ability to shape it; they will feel empowered.

Since the study is limited to one region, conducting a national survey to assess the ESC-participating schools is highly recommended.

References

Abiva, M., (2016). The Facilitating and the Hindering Factors in Implementing Government Assistance to Students and Teachers in Private Education (GASTPE) Program and Its Contribution to the Participating Secondary Schools. <http://sherj.smccnasipit.edu.ph/articles/Vol2/Abiva.pdf>

Baker, B. (2019). School Facilities Matter! In so many ways (how could they not?). <https://schoolfinance101.wordpress.com/2019/08/26/school-facilities-matter-in-so-many-ways-how-could-they-not/>

Bediako, S. (2019). Models and Concepts of Curriculum Implementation, Some Definitions and Influence of Implementation.

https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333338710_Models_and_concepts_of_curriculum_implementation_some_definitions_and_influence_of_implementation

Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2013). *Successful qualitative research: A practical guide for beginners*. London, UK: SAGE.

Brender, J. (2006). *Framework for Meta-Assessment of Assessment Studies*. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/social-sciences/triangulation>

Brewster, C. & Larson, H. (1992). Human resource management in Europe: Evidence from 10 countries. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, Vol. 3 No. 3, pp. 409-34.

Buckner, K. (2020). *School Principal: The Role of Elementary and Secondary School Principals, Principal Duties and Responsibilities, Principal Qualifications*. <https://education.stateuniversity.com/pages/2333/Principal-School.html>

Chen, G. (2020). *Smaller Class Sizes: Pros and Cons*. <https://www.publicschoolreview.com/blog/smaller-class-sizes-pros-and-cons>

Cornelio, G. (2016). *CPBRD Policy Brief Reformation Directions for the eEducation servicecontracting scheme*. https://www.academia.edu/22374700/CPBRD_Policy_Brief_Reformation_Directions_for_the_eEducation_service_contracting_scheme

Daisyme, P. (2012). *4 Things That Will Give Employees a Sense of Ownership*. <https://due.com/blog/sense-of-ownership>

Delgado, P. (2019). *The Importance of Parental Involvement in Teaching*. <https://observatory.tec.mx/edu-news/the-importance-of-parental-involvement-in-teaching>

Durham, J. (2020). *What is Meant by 'Spiritual Growth'?* <http://www.lifecoachexpert.co.uk/what-is-meant-by-spiritual-growth.html#:~:>

Flavia, J. (2012). *Importance of Budgeting in Schools*. <https://www.kenyaplex.com/resources/6041-importance-of-budgeting-in-schools.aspx>

Felipe, A. & Porio, C. (2010). *NEW ROUTES TO PRIVATE HIGH SCHOOLS: New Schemes Based on School Choice*. <https://www.google.com.ph/search?q=new+research+study+about+education+service+contracting&dcr=0&ei=jBVXXt75LNfj->

Franklin, D. (2019). *The Courage to Speak Up*. <https://davidfranklin.org/the-courage-to-speak-up/>

Galias, M. (n.d.). *Transparency Board: Ensuring Accountability in the Use of School MOOE*. <https://www.teacherph.com/transparency-board-more/>

Hamilton, S. (2017). *How School Facilities Affect Student Performance*. <https://classroom.synonym.com/school-facilities-affect-student-performance-16960.html>

Kennedy, R. (2020). *Why Private School?* <https://www.privateschoolreview.com/blog/why-private-school>

Langen, A. (2015). *Chapter 3 Research Design and Methodology*. <http://www.ais.utm.my/researchportal/files/2015/02/Example3-Res-Design.pdf>

Lazere, E. (2019). *Transparency: A Key to Education Equity and Better School Budgets*. <https://www.dcfpi.org/all/transparency-a-key-to-education-equity-and-better-school-budgets/>

Mateo, (2019). *Updates on the GASTPE Programs*. <https://peac.org.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/12/1-Usec.-Jesus-Mateo-Updates-on-the-GASTPE-Programs.pdf>

Merriam, S. B. (2009). *Qualitative Research: A Guide to Design and Implementation*. San Francisco, CA: Wiley, John & Sons, Incorporated.

Paget, V. (2019). *3 Reasons Why School Administration Is Important For Student Education*. <https://blog.boardingware.com/3-reasons-why-school-administration-is-important-for-student-education/>

PAO, (2018). *Government Assistance to Students and Teachers in Private Education*. https://www.coa.gov.ph/phocadownload/userupload/performance-audit-report/2018/PAO_2018-02_GASTPE.pdf

PEAC, (2018). *2018 Certification Assessment Instrument*. <https://peac.org.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/06/2018-2019-THE-FINAL-CAI-1.pdf>

Penn State University, (2017). *The Importance of School Facilities in Improving Student Outcomes*. <https://interioravenue.net/2017/11/06/improving-student-outcomes/#:~:>

Saguin, K. (2019). *Designing effective governance of education*. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/25741292.20191621034>

- Stauffer, B. (2020). What Is a Curriculum and How Do You Make One? <https://www.aeseducation.com/blog/what-is-a-curriculum>
- UNICEF, (2020). Teachers: Leading in Crisis, Reimagining the Future. <https://www.unicef.org/press-releases/teachers-leading-crisis-reimagining-future>
- Uytico, (2018). DepEd bares education challenges in Eastern Visayas. <https://ptvnews.ph/depd-bares-education-challenges-eastern>
- Velez, E. & Patrinos, H. (2011). PHILIPPINES Private Provision, Public Purpose. A Review of the Government's Education Service Contracting Program. <http://documents.worldbank.org/curated/en/486651468092652040/Philippines-Private-provision-public-purpose-a-review-of-the-governments-education->
- Yin, R.K. (2003). *Case Study Research: Design and Methods*, 3rd ed., Sage, London

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